

Leveraging Anisotropic Error for Robust Point Cloud Registration

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Abstract—Point Cloud Registration (PCR) is a fundamental task in 3D perception, with applications in Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM), 3D reconstruction, object recognition, and autonomous navigation. It involves aligning two or more point clouds into a common coordinate system, a process that is often challenged by noise, outliers, and variations in point density. Traditional registration methods, such as Iterative Closest Point (ICP) and its variants, rely on minimizing point-to-point or point-to-plane distances, but they may struggle in the presence of anisotropic errors and misaligned correspondences. In this work, we propose a novel point cloud registration method that incorporates an anisotropic error model to better account for the underlying geometric structure of the data. Utilizing key results from Linear Algebra, we derive theoretical guarantees on the robustness of our approach. Our method ensures position and orientation consistency of matched pairs by analyzing the covariance structure of registration errors, reducing the impact of outliers and enhancing the stability of the alignment process. Experimental results of this study provide valuable insights into the role of covariance modeling in point cloud registration and open new possibilities for improving the reliability of 3D perception in robotics, autonomous systems, and augmented reality applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

Depth sensing technology has become increasingly vital in areas like robotics, autonomous vehicles, and augmented reality, as it allows machines to effectively perceive and understand their environment, even under low-light conditions, where traditional cameras struggle. Depth sensors, such as LiDARs, create depth maps of their surroundings in the form of point clouds.

Point Cloud Registration (PCR) is the process of aligning multiple point clouds into a common coordinate system by finding the spatial transformations that relate them. Preliminary work in PCR, includes [1] and [2], which both derived closed-form solutions for the least squares optimal rigid and similarity transformations between two point sets with known point-to-point correspondence. [1] uses Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), while [2] employs quaternions. These results were important because they were subsequently used in algorithms like [3], [4].

The first significant milestone in the field of PCR was the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm [3]. ICP addresses the registration problem in an iterative, expectation-maximization-like manner [5]. Starting from an initial estimate for the transformation, ICP alternates between two steps: the correspondence and the optimization step [6]. ICP updates the correspondence based on the current transformation estimate during the correspondence step. In the optimization step, the algorithm

refines the transformation based on the newly established correspondence through optimization. This process is repeated until the algorithm converges. It has been demonstrated that the algorithm converges to a local minimum of the original registration problem [7].

The authors in [8] deviated from the point-to-point error metric used in ICP and its variants by introducing the point-to-plane metric. This metric represents the projection of the error vector along the direction of the normal vector. The resulting algorithm, known as Point-To-Plane ICP, achieves significantly faster convergence than the traditional ICP, highlighting the advantages of incorporating additional geometric information beyond the locations of the points into the registration process. In this work [9], the authors introduce a unified framework that generalizes ICP and Point-To-Plane ICP, referred to as Generalized ICP (GICP). GICP employs covariance matrices to represent the local geometry at each point [10]. This formulation facilitated the development of the renowned Plane-To-Plane ICP, which addresses the asymmetry of Point-To-Plane ICP [11]. Normal ICP (NICP) [12] enhances GICP by integrating the normals into the optimization process. Recently, data-driven techniques for constructing the covariance matrices [13] have opened up new horizons, providing further opportunities to enhance the efficiency of the framework.

The Normal Distribution Transform (NDT) [14], firstly divides the space occupied by the first point cloud into uniformly sized cells. Then, for each cell, the mean and covariance matrix of the points within the cell are computed. The likelihood of a point of the second point cloud being at a specific location within a cell is then modeled using the normal distribution with mean and covariance matrix corresponding to that of the cell that contains the point. Newton's algorithm is applied, iteratively refining the pose parameters.

In the Coherent Point Drift (CPD) algorithm [4], the points of the first point cloud are considered to be the centroids of a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) and the second point cloud is considered to be generated by this GMM. The optimal transformation is the one that maximizes the likelihood of the second point cloud under the GMM of the first. To solve this optimization problem, the Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm is employed. The name of the algorithm stems from the fact that the GMM centroids move coherently as a group, preserving the topological structure of the point set during the registration process. An extension of this method to register multiple point sets called Joint Registration of Multiple Point Clouds (JRMPC) is discussed in [15]. The authors in [16] proposed a method called CPD with Local Surface Geometry (LSG-CPD) which extends CPD with anisotropic

Fig. 1: Above, we observe the behavior of the eigenvalues $\nu_1 \geq \nu_2$ of the sum of two covariance matrices A and B , each with the same set of eigenvalues $\{1, \epsilon\}$ in two dimensions, with respect to their relative orientation α . Below, we display the isosurfaces of three Gaussian random variables a, b and $a + b$ with covariance matrices A, B and $A + B$ as a function of the relative orientation between A and B .

Gaussian components. GMM-based techniques are powerful and flexible, but also computationally demanding. This sets challenges for their integration in real-time applications.

In this work, we propose a method based on an anisotropic error model in the style of [8], [9], [16]. Then, we leverage key results from Linear Algebra to demonstrate its robustness against outliers by ensuring the position and orientation consistency of the matched pairs. This work enhances the theoretical understanding of error propagation in point cloud registration, contributing to more robust and accurate 3D alignment techniques. By analyzing the interaction between covariance matrices and eigenvector orientations, it provides valuable insights for improving registration performance. The main contribution of this work is summarized below:

- We introduce a probabilistic error model for point registration that analyzes the impact of summing covariance matrices on the registration process, providing a theoretical foundation for understanding error propagation in point cloud alignment.
- We use Weyl's Inequality to derive bounds on the eigenvalues of the summed covariance matrices, providing useful insights into how the alignment of eigenvectors affects the distribution of registration errors.
- We demonstrate that the alignment of eigenvectors of covariance matrices influences the shape of the error distribution, which highlights that when eigenvectors are aligned, the error distribution remains elliptical, preserving positional consistency. Conversely, when they are perpendicular, the distribution becomes spherical, reducing the influence of outliers.

II. METHOD

In our analysis, each data point p is modeled as $p = s + e$, where s represents the true point's position, p is the measured point's position, and e is the error vector. We assume that the

error vector e has a Gaussian distribution with zero mean and covariance matrix Σ , $e \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma)$. For two measurements of s , $p_1 = s + e_1$ and $p_2 = s + e_2$, assuming that $e_1 \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_1)$ and $e_2 \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_2)$ and that e_1 and e_2 are independent, for the difference $d = p_1 - p_2 = e_1 - e_2$ we have $d \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma)$, where $\Sigma = \Sigma_1 + \Sigma_2$. We then search for the transformation which maximizes the likelihood of the differences which is equivalent to:

$$T^* = \arg \min_T \sum_i d_i^T \Sigma_i^{-1} d_i. \quad (1)$$

We assume that the error e exhibits anisotropy along a single axis - the set of eigenvalues of Σ has the form $\{1, 1, \epsilon\}$ - adopting the model proposed in [9], where the deviation of e along the normal direction is smaller.

The main purpose of this paper is the analysis of the behavior of the sum $\Sigma_1 + \Sigma_2$, the resulting distribution of the difference d , and the significant impact of our results on the registration process. The behavior of the eigenvalues (the spectrum) of the sum of two symmetric matrices, given the eigenvalues of the individual matrices, was first studied by Weyl [17], [18]. One major result, known as *Weyl's Inequality*, provides important bounds on the eigenvalues of the sum of two symmetric matrices.

Theorem 1 (Weyl's Inequality). *Let A and B be two $n \times n$ symmetric matrices with eigenvalues $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_n$ and $\mu_1 \geq \mu_2 \geq \dots \geq \mu_n$, respectively. Then, for the eigenvalues $\nu_1 \geq \nu_2 \geq \dots \geq \nu_n$ of the sum $A + B$, the following bounds hold:*

$$\nu_{i+j-1} \leq \lambda_i + \mu_j \leq \nu_{i+j-n} \quad (2)$$

for all $1 \leq i, j \leq n, i + j - 1 \leq n, i + j - n \geq 1$.

Applying Eq. (2) for $n = 3$ and the specific form of the matrices A and B , we obtain the bounds for the eigenvalues ν_1, ν_2, ν_3 of the sum $\Sigma_1 + \Sigma_2$, which are $\nu_1 = 2$, $\nu_2 \in [1 + \epsilon, 2]$, $\nu_3 \in [2\epsilon, 1 + \epsilon]$. In addition, due to the symmetry of the problem with respect to the first two eigenvalues of Σ_1 and Σ_2 , we can make the following statement:

Lemma 2. *The spectrum of the sum $\Sigma_1 + \Sigma_2$, and consequently the distribution of d , depends only on the angle between the eigenvectors of A and B corresponding to their respective minimal eigenvalues. When the eigenvectors are aligned, the minimum eigenvalue of $\Sigma_1 + \Sigma_2$ reaches its minimum value, 2ϵ , and d has an elliptical distribution. When the eigenvectors are perpendicular, the minimum eigenvalue of $A + B$ reaches its maximum value, $1 + \epsilon$, and d a spherical distribution.*

To demonstrate these statements, we employ the experimental procedure described below. We need to examine the possible sets of eigenvalues $\{\nu_1, \dots, \nu_n\}$ of the sum of two symmetric matrices A, B that share the same set of eigenvalues $\{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n\} = \{1, 1, \dots, \epsilon\}$. We denote $q_1^1, q_2^1, \dots, q_1^n$ as the eigenvectors of A , and $q_1^2, q_2^2, \dots, q_2^n$ as the eigenvectors of B , corresponding to $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n$, respectively. To generate the set of matrices with spectrum $\lambda = \{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n\}$, we use the formula $A = Q\Lambda Q^T$, where $\Lambda = \text{diag}\{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n\}$ and Q is a matrix in the set $\mathcal{O}(n)$ of $n \times n$ orthogonal matrices.

For $n = 2$, we can span $\mathcal{O}(2)$ using a single parameter α by setting $Q = [\cos(\alpha), -\sin(\alpha); \sin(\alpha), \cos(\alpha)]$.

TABLE I: The effect of ϵ in the registration performance. With (w.p.) we denote the times including the preprocessing.

Metric	Ours ($\epsilon = 4e - 4$)	Ours ($\epsilon = 2e - 2$)	Ours ($\epsilon = 1$)	ICP
Mean Translation Error (m)	0.0055	0.0374	0.1783	0.1782
Max Translation Error (m)	0.0150	0.0741	0.4620	0.4620
Mean Rotation Error (°)	0.1463	0.4921	2.5843	2.5633
Max Rotation Error (°)	0.2894	1.4364	6.1566	6.1017
Mean Iterations	5.5667	11.1	29.3667	29
Max Iterations	12	21	125	126
Mean Execution Time (sec)	0.1198	0.2203	0.5517	0.5042
Max Execution Time (sec)	0.2571	0.4331	2.8620	2.6690
Mean Execution Time (w.p.) (sec)	0.1823	0.2829	0.5592	0.5137
Max Execution Time (w.p.) (sec)	0.3192	0.5029	2.8913	2.6913

TABLE II: Comparison of NDT, GICP (BFGS), GICP (Newton), and Our Method. For GICP we use two different optimizers BFGS and Newton.

Metric	NDT	GICP (BFGS)	GICP (Newton)	Ours
Mean Translation Error (m)	0.0372	0.0058	0.0054	0.0055
Max Translation Error (m)	0.0741	0.0151	0.0150	0.0150
Mean Rotation Error (°)	0.4836	0.1447	0.1439	0.1463
Max Rotation Error (°)	1.4370	0.2894	0.2880	0.2894
Mean Iterations	11.200	5.500	5.5333	5.5667
Max Iterations	28	14	13	12
Mean Execution Time (sec)	-	0.2928	0.2587	0.1198
Max Execution Time (sec)	-	0.6425	0.5224	0.2571
Mean Execution Time (w.p.) (sec)	0.5731	0.3554	0.3224	0.1823
Max Execution Time (w.p.) (sec)	1.2042	0.6993	0.5821	0.3192

By constructing B for various values of α , while keeping $A = \Lambda$, we can explore all possible relative orientations between A and B , compute the sums $A + B$, and evaluate the corresponding eigenvalues. We also draw the isosurfaces (isocurves) of three Gaussians with covariance matrices A , B , and $A + B$ in red, green and blue respectively (down). The isosurfaces of $\mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma)$ have the form $e^T \Sigma^{-1} e = \text{const}$, which represent ellipses. From Weyl’s inequality, we get $v_1 \in [1 + \epsilon, 2]$, $v_2 \in [2\epsilon, 1 + \epsilon]$. The validity of these bounds are verified in the figure (up). We observe that when q_1^1 and q_2^1 (equivalently q_1^2 and q_2^2) are aligned, the maximum eigenvalue v_1 and the minimum eigenvalue v_2 of $A + B$ attain their maximum and minimum values, 2 and 2ϵ , respectively and the isosurfaces of $\mathcal{N}(0, A + B)$ have an elliptical shape. When q_1^1 and q_2^1 are perpendicular, v_1 and v_2 attain their minimum and maximum values, $1 + \epsilon$ and $1 + \epsilon$, respectively and the isosurfaces of $\mathcal{N}(0, A + B)$ have a spherical shape.

For $n = 3$, from Weyl’s inequality, we get $v_1 = 2$, $v_2 \in [1 + \epsilon, 2]$, $v_3 \in [2\epsilon, 1 + \epsilon]$. Due to the symmetry of the specific problem regarding the first two eigenvalues, the spectrum of $A + B$ depends on the angle between the eigenvectors q_1^3 and q_2^3 of A and B that correspond to the minimum eigenvalue λ_3 in a manner similar to that presented for $n = 2$. These results are illustrated in Figure Fig. 1.

In conclusion, when the eigenvectors are aligned, the shape of the distribution of the sum retains the shape of the distribution of its constituent parts. When the eigenvectors are perpendicular, the distribution loses the shape of the constituent distributions. This behavior ensures position and orientation consistency in matched pairs during registration. Given that $\epsilon \ll 1$, when the normals of two corresponding points are not aligned (i.e., in the case of outlier matching), the effect of the pair on the registration cost is minimal.

A. Neighborhood Analysis and Construction of the Covariance Matrices

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is the most fundamental technique for extracting information about the local structure of the surface in the vicinity of a point by analyzing its neighborhood. In practice, the “neighborhood” of a point is typically defined as the set of points within a specified range from the point or its k Nearest Neighbors (k NN). The PCA of a set of points $\{p_i\}_{i=1}^K$ is the eigenanalysis of its covariance matrix

$$C = \sum_{i=1}^K (p_i - \bar{p})(p_i - \bar{p})^T$$

The eigenvectors of C are related to the orientation of the surface in space. Specifically, the eigenvector associated with the smallest eigenvalue indicates the direction of the normal vector of the surface at the specific point.

B. Optimization on the group of 3D Euclidean Transformations

We search for a rigid transformation that solves the registration problem. An Euclidean or rigid transformation is a geometric transformation that can be expressed as $p' = Rp + t$, where R is a rotation matrix, and t is a translation vector. If p is a random vector with covariance matrix C_p , an Euclidean transformation, also transforms its covariance matrix as: $C_{p'} = RC_p R^T$. In three-dimensional space, any rotation can be expressed as a composition of three rotations around the coordinate axes:

$$R(a_x, a_y, a_z) = R_z(a_z) \cdot R_y(a_y) \cdot R_x(a_x) \quad (3)$$

So any 3D Euclidean transformation can be encoded using a 6 parameter vector $\theta = [t_x, t_y, t_z, a_x, a_y, a_z]^T$, consisting of three translational and three angular components.

The fundamental step of this method [19] is substituting the optimization function in Eq. (1) at each step with its quadratic approximation, evaluated at the point under consideration in the parameter space. Once the objective function is replaced by its quadratic approximation, we minimize the latter instead. The advantage of this substitution is that, unlike the original function, we can determine the minimum of the quadratic approximation in closed form.

III. RESULTS

The ETH Laser Registration Dataset [20] comprises eight point cloud sequences recorded in diverse environments, ranging from indoor apartments to woodland areas, offering a benchmark for evaluating registration methods across various real-world scenarios. The metrics we use to evaluate the registration performance include the mean and maximum translation and rotation offset, the mean and maximum number of iterations, and the mean and maximum computation time. Given the ground truth absolute poses of two point clouds A_i and A_j , we extract the relative pose (ground truth transformation) between them using: $A_{ij} = A_i^{-1} A_j$. The metrics that we use to evaluate the offset between the estimated transformation (R, t) and the ground truth transformation (R^*, t^*) are the following:

$$\text{errt} = \|t - t^*\|, \quad \text{errr} = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\text{trace}(RR^{*-1}) - 1}{2} \right)$$

Registration of two scans (Bird's eye view)

Registration of two scans (Side view)

Reconstruction of the scene using all the available scans.

Fig 2. Registration results on the ETH "Stairs" dataset using ICP, which is based on an isotropic error model and our method which is based on an anisotropic error model. We mark the significant registration artifacts of the former.

The first experiment aims to analyze the effect of the anisotropic error model on registration performance. Table I presents the results for the "Stairs" sequence of the ETH dataset. We observe that the anisotropic error model accelerates convergence in terms of both iterations and computation time (despite the additional computational cost of the estimation of the normals) while significantly improving registration accuracy in both translation and rotation. Decreasing ϵ enhances this effect; however, excessively small values of ϵ can lead to numerical instability. When $\epsilon = 1$, the optimization problem in Eq. (1) is equivalent to that of ICP, and we validate that both methods converge to the same solution. Although ICP is faster, as it is the optimal algorithm for its specific problem, it cannot handle the general anisotropic case of the optimization problem in Eq. (1).

The second experiment compares our method with similar approaches that incorporate geometric information into the registration process, such as NDT and GICP. While NDT uses normal information for only one point cloud, GICP uses normal information for both. For GICP, we employ two different optimizers: BFGS and the more efficient Newton method. In Table II, we present the results for the "Stairs"

sequence of the ETH dataset. Our method outperforms NDT in both speed and accuracy, and also surpasses GICP in terms of speed. The improvement with respect to GICP can be attributed to the algorithm we developed in [19].

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, we introduced a novel PCR method using an anisotropic error model and key principles from Linear Algebra to enhance alignment robustness. The proposed approach ensures position and orientation consistency, mitigating the effects of outliers and noise, by analyzing the covariance structure of registration errors. The experimental analysis emphasised that our method achieves faster convergence and higher accuracy compared to existing techniques. These findings highlight the importance of incorporating geometric error modeling into point cloud registration to improve performance in real-world applications. Future work will focus on extending our approach to large-scale point cloud datasets, exploring adaptive weighting strategies for covariance estimation, and integrating our method with real-time SLAM and 3D reconstruction pipelines.

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